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A STUDY OF PERFORMANCE MANAGEMENT SYSTEM IN WIPRO

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Abstract

The study aims to study and analyze Performance Management components and their usage in Wipro. The study entailed detailed examination of the methods to measure and enhance performance management system against its objectives. Exploratory research followed by descriptive research has been used in the study. Non-probability convenience sampling has been used in the study. The sample size is 40. Primary data has been collected using two structured questionnaires. Depth interview method was used by which answers to the questionnaire were sought. The performance management system is an integral part of an organization to measure, motivate, and improve the performance of the entire organization. It also helps to focus on the goals of the organization towards specific pre-determined objectives for an organizational culture. The companies must identify and develop unique retention strategies to retain the employees. An established formal communication networking with an informal focus would give the organizations an additional competitive advantage.

Keywords: critical incidence, paired comparison, retention, self appraisal, succession planning.

Introduction

Performance is what is expected to be delivered by an individual or a set of individuals within a time frame. What is expected to be delivered could be stated in terms of results or efforts, tasks and quality, with specification of conditions under which it is to be delivered.

Concerns of performance management

The following are the main concerns of performance management:

- Concern with outputs, outcomes, process and input
- Concern with planning
- Concern with measurement and review
- Concern with continuous improvement
- Concern with continuous development
- Concern for better communication

- Concern for stakeholders
- Concern for fairness and transparency

The process of performance management

Performance management should be regarded as a flexible *process*, not as a 'system'. The use of the term 'system' implies a rigid, standardized and bureaucratic approach, which is inconsistent with the concept of performance management as a flexible and evolutionary, albeit coherent, process that is applied by managers working with their teams in accordance with the circumstances in which they operate.

Performance management is a natural process of management. As defined by the total quality expert William Deming; it consists of these basic activities:

- *Plan* – decide what to do and how to do it.
- *Act* – carry out the work needed to implement the plan.
- *Monitor* – carry out continuous checks on what is being done and measure outcomes in order to assess progress in implementing the plan.
- *Review* – consider what has been achieved and, in the light of this, establish what more needs to be done and any corrective action required if performance is not in line with the plan.

Performance management in action

Performance management should not be treated as a mechanistic system based on periodical formal appraisals and detailed documentation. These activities should be coherent in the sense of contributing to an overall systematic approach in which all aspects of the performance management process are aligned. Thus there needs to be a declaration of intent, which states why performance management is important, how it works and how people will be affected by it. Examples of how such an approach is made are given below.

Organizational performance measures: It is necessary to measure achievements and progress against objectives, and organizations have therefore to decide what measures should be used. A few key measures owned by more than one function are more effective than a multiplicity of measures – this avoids the problem faced by many organizations of 'drowning in data'.

The key measures are likely to include those concerned with:

- *Financial performance* – for example sales, profits, return on capital employed, economic value added, earnings per share, price/earnings ratio.
- *Operational performance* – these measures will be related to the critical success factors. For example, in a retail store these could include level of service to customers and customer satisfaction, stock availability and stock wastage. A manufacturing company might use measures of quality, throughput, inventory control and delivery.
- *People performance* – for example profit, sales or added value per employee, payroll costs as a percentage of sales, output per employee (productivity), retention rates, employee satisfaction.

The balanced scorecard: The balanced scorecard as originally developed by Kaplan and Norton is frequently used as the basis for measurement. Managers want a balanced presentation of both financial and operational measures.'

Their original concept of the scorecard required managers to answer four basic questions, which means looking at the business from four related perspectives:

- How do customers see us? (Customer perspective.)
- What must we excel at? (Internal perspective.)
- Can we continue to improve and create value? (Innovation and learning perspective.)
- How do we look at shareholders? (Financial perspective.)

The balanced scorecard approach ‘puts strategy and vision, not control at the centre’. It defines goals, it assumes that people will adopt whatever behaviors’ and take whatever actions are required to achieve those goals: ‘Senior managers may know what the end result should be, but they cannot tell employees exactly how to achieve that result, if only because the conditions in which employees operate are constantly changing.’ Kaplan and Norton suggest that building a scorecard enables a company to link its financial budgets with its strategic goals. The balanced scorecard can help to align employees’ individual performance with the overall strategy: ‘Scorecard users generally engage in three activities: communicating and educating, setting goals and linking rewards to performance measures.’

Scope of the study

The performance of the employees is being analyzed which can indirectly influence the satisfaction of the employee and directly motivates them to work for the organizational development. The study helps to analyze the trends in performance management system in Wipro industry and give appropriate suggestions to improve the practices taken by it.

Literature review

Forslund (2007) a state-of-the-art description of the activities in logistics performance management is provided, addressing the following questions in dyadic relationships: how often are expectations updated? Who is the customer's contact person? What is the contract situation? Which actor (customer or supplier) formulates performance targets, and who measures logistics performance? Some of these issues' relationships to customers' expected logistics performance were verified.

Lo & Chin (2009) The seven user-satisfaction-based core values, eight critical success factors and five-phase knowledge management process are identified as the basis of the assessment criteria. These assessment criteria provide academics and practitioners with a new insight into the research landscape for knowledge management performance measurement.

Adobor (2004) focuses on management processes in shared-managed joint ventures. It suggests that the evolution and effectiveness of the management team in joint ventures may be facilitated by certain key contextual and individual level factors. Looking at venture management as an inter-organizational group of people composed of

members representing parent organizations whose behavior is regulated by a common set of expectations can give clues to the special nature of joint venture management tasks. The individuals nominated to the team as well as some key performance-facilitating contextual factors may affect team effectiveness.

Gomes & Yasin (2011) the advocated approach integrates several frameworks in an effort to address practical concerns related to performance measurement, management, and improvement.

Boland & Fowler (2000) the potential role of influence diagrams and dynamic simulation models is thereby introduced as a potential means of unraveling the complex behavior which can often arise in the presence of such interactive cause-effect loops. A number of typical examples, drawn from within the public sector, are invoked to illustrate the discussion.

Busi & Bititci (2006) there is a lack of understanding of what collaboration means and what it implies on the development of appropriate performance measurement systems. Future research should study the nature of collaboration and the characteristics of performance indicators to support it.

Agyemang & Ryan (2013) examines organizational change processes that occur when accountability demands from powerful external stakeholders change. It investigates, firstly, whether these external accountability demands impact on the performance management systems of two different types of organizations. Secondly, it considers whether the goals for improved performance contained within the external accountability demands are realized. In the public sector case study, the organizations tended to reorient their performance management systems towards the external accountability demands; whilst in the private sector organization, pressures from falling share prices forced managers to focus their decision making on the preferred performance measures contained in shareholders' accountability demands.

Bourne et al (2003) there is a growing trend towards managing performance improvement through focusing on the underlying drivers of performance, whether improvements in the processes or the underlying resources that give these processes capability. The past obsession with pure financial performance is decreasing and there may be recognition that there is a trade off between hitting today's financial results and sustaining the capabilities and competences that allow companies to compete effectively in the future.

Willis & Willis (1996) Engineering consulting firms involved in the design and construction of large-scale industrial plants attempt to find flaws as early as possible in the design process to avoid more costly deviation corrections later on, particularly during and after construction. Deviation corrections can be reduced by pursuing more diligent quality prevention and appraisal efforts. Quality performance management system (QPMS) is a cost evaluation programme designed to measure the prevention and appraisal effort and its impact on deviation corrections.

Schiama (2012) Knowledge represents one of the fundamental constituent parts of any organization and it can be incorporated into people's abilities or ingrained into structural and technological capital. Thus management of knowledge is at the core of organization's business growth. In the light of this reflection this special issue pays attention to two main perspectives. First, recognizing that knowledge, likewise any other organization's resource, needs management means to support its allocation and development, the frameworks and tools aiming to identify, manage and assess the critical knowledge resources for growth are focused on. Second, acknowledging that the translation of knowledge into business outcomes requires management mechanisms, and then considering the knowledge processes grounding the improvement of performance.

Research methodology

Objectives:

- To study the existing system prevailing with regard to performance management system in Wipro.
- To focus on the challenges prevailing in the retention of such highly skilled effective employees.
- To provide some meaningful suggestions to the organizations as well as the industry to improve, modify and change the existing systems of performance management.

Research design: Exploratory research followed by descriptive research has been used in the study. Descriptive studies are undertaken in many circumstances. When the researcher is interested in knowing the characteristics of certain groups such as age, sex, educational level, occupation or income, a descriptive study is necessary. Descriptive studies are well-structured. It tends to be signed and its approach cannot be changed every now and then. It is, therefore necessary that the research give sufficient thought to framing research questions and deciding the types of data to be collected for their purpose.

Sampling Technique: Non-probability convenience sampling has been used in the study. Convenience sampling refers to the collection of information from members of the population who are conveniently available to provide it. It is most often used during the exploratory phase and is perhaps the best way of getting some basic information quickly and efficiently.

Sample size: The study has been carried out by collecting information from Wipro by using simple random sampling. The sample size is 40.

Data collection tools: In the study data has been collected using primary and secondary methods of data collection. Primary data has been collected using two structured questionnaires. Depth interview method has been used. Secondary data has been collected from journals, articles; research magazines and working papers available in the organization and from Internet.

Data analysis

The components of performance management system in Wipro are as follows:

- When and how are the Key Result Areas (KRAs) for an employee identified? How are the changes in KRAs handled if the business requirements change?

Wipro follows top down approach. The organizational goals are cascaded down the line i.e. through organizational goals, KRAs of top management is set then from those KRAs, KRAs of others managers at various levels are set. Various heads further sets KRAs of team leaders through team meetings. If management comes to know that there are people with below average performance, they provide them with performance improvement training. It is an online process in Wipro.

- What are the components / phases of performance management system?

In Wipro G & O i.e. Goals and Objective setting is the first step of Performance Management System. Appraisal is done annually starting from April to March. The appraisal period in Wipro changes from year to year. There is a

reward system which is generally in monetary form. After doing Wipro leadership survey in the company, which is done annually in the company and at high band level, star performers are recognized and groomed. Performance appraisal which is an important part of performance management system in Wipro requires self appraisal of employees on both lower and higher level of hierarchy. 360 degree feedback is only done at middle and higher level. There is a face to face meeting with the employee after self appraisal. After this the whole process rating is provided to the employee i.e. GP rating, then according to the rating, rewards in form of monetary hikes are provided to employees. Various development and improvement programs are conducted for the employees on the basis of the need after the appraisal has been taken place.

- How many meetings are scheduled in a year to discuss employee performance?

Minimum one meeting is preferable in a year to discuss the employee performance in Wipro.

- Which technique is adopted for carrying out performance appraisal? Is it different for senior level managers?

In Wipro performance appraisal is done through face to face interviews, which is done after self appraisal. One on one interview appraisal method is chosen by Wipro because it helps in clarity of results given and communicated by supervisor. Communication between employee and manager is better. Wipro also has 360 degree feedback mechanism which includes feedback from peers, clients, subordinates and immediate boss. In Wipro appraisal is an online process.

- Does the company use tools to reduce biasness in the PMS?

In Wipro, the appraisal system is total online and they use normalization method to reduce biasness in the system.

- What all processes are part of your PMS?

In Wipro importance on career management is relatively more since it is considered light path for employees. Career management and development plan of employees helps them to grow as a person and develop their hidden potential which in turn helps the company to have more talent pool in the company which would be definitely a positive for the growth of the company.

- How are the Training and Development (T&D) needs captured through the process of performance appraisal?

Wipro assess training and development needs, if it has been suggested by the boss or during the self appraisal period appraiser feels that there is a need for training and development in certain areas. There is also a strategic leadership development team for training and development position. There is also PCCP department for assessing training and development needs.

- How succession planning is done in your organization?

In Wipro, succession planning is done through the suggestion of managers. Managers suggest some names and nominees are chosen from them by top management. Top management conducts interview with nominees and make their decisions accordingly.

- What is the most important aspect of PMS?

Wipro like HCL also gives high weight age to retention of employees and makes it a huge part of their performance management system. Identification of training and development needs of employees and motivating the employees are also a part of performance management system.

- Which rating scale is used by the company? Is there any standard approach for rating the employee?

Wipro uses GP rating ‘G’ stands for process/ performance of an employee over a period of time and ‘P’ stands for personal effectiveness. Wipro follows a 5 level grid. Every employee is rated on this grid. Rating is from G1P1 to G5p5. G1P1 is the lowest rating which an employee can get and G5P5 is the highest rating. According to the rating, employees are distributed on bell curve. The percentage of bell curve differs from year to year.

- Is promotion part of the PMS? How are incentives and promotions linked to the PMS outcome? What are the criteria for promotion? What percentage (%) of the eligible population is allowed for promotions every year?

Wipro provides internal promotions twice a year to its employees. Promotion of employees is finalized with the help of their appraisal. Anyone can be a part of promotion exercise who joins between 1st Jan to 31st march. Usually employees with grading of G3P3 and above are eligible for promotions as the 5 level grids are followed by Wipro. These rating helps when there are some GAPS in organization and it is required to be filled. Wipro has slide system for it in which internal promotions are done through nomination which helps in filling the gap. It is done twice a year. Another method of promotion which is followed by Wipro is through IJPC i.e. internal job posting. It is done every quarterly i.e. in every 4 months and completed in 45 days before quarterly results are out. In this method first aptitude tests are taken followed by group discussion and panel interviews. When an employee passes all the stages, the promotion is granted to him.

- How are Compensation & Rewards connected to the PMS?

Compensation to employees in Wipro is given according to the GP rating and where they fall in bell curve distribution. Compensation is benchmarked after taking up organization wide survey. The benchmarking process is done by third party i.e. Hewitt. Wipro outsources the benchmarking process to Hewitt and Hewitt provides them with relevant data.

PMS fact sheet

Table 1: showing phases of PMS in company

Phases of PMS	Performance Appraisal Year	Objective Setting	Performance Review Period	Training & Development	Salary Review
WIPRO	1 st Jan- 31 st Dec	Existing employees: Jan-Feb New Joinees: Within 30 days of joining	April – March	Training calendar is released at the end of performance appraisal period	By Jan

Table 2: showing a few parameters of PMS

Parameters	WIPRO
<i>Identification of KRAs</i>	G & O setting (Jan – Feb)
<i>No. of meetings</i>	Min. one
<i>Tools used for reducing biasness</i>	Normalization
<i>Part of PMS</i>	Career management, T & D
<i>Assessment of T & D needs</i>	SLDP
<i>Rating scales</i>	GP rating
<i>Succession Planning</i>	By the suggestion of managers
<i>Strategy linkage</i>	Retention strategy, T & D
<i>percentage promotions</i>	10%

Findings

Following are the findings of the study:

- For reducing the biasness in PMS normalization is used mostly.
- Training of the employees is an important part of PMS.
- Retention of the employees is of utmost importance while making policies regarding PMS in the company.
- If poor performance of an employee is identified, there is a trend of providing improvement coaching.

Recommendations

Following are the recommendations for improving the overall PMS in the company studied:

- Biannual performance review should be started with the next review period.
- As it is inferred that PMS system is important for any organization, the organizations must invest in specific technology oriented products and services, software and hardware to improve the performance.
- Self appraisal is the most effective tool for PMS system, so the management must effectively develop training and development tools to make the employees sensitive towards the organizational environment and culture.
- Training and development, career development and succession planning become the core essential functions of a PMS. The organizations must concentrate on these areas to effectively appraise and improve the performance of employees in the organizations.
- Retention and innovation strategies are used to improve the performance of employees, so the focus must be directed towards improving the PMS.

Conclusions

The performance management system is an integral part of an organization to measure, motivate, and improve the performance of the entire organization. It also helps to focus on the goals of the organization towards specific pre-determined objectives for an organizational culture. The companies must identify and develop unique retention strategies to retain the employees. An established formal communication networking with an informal focus would give the organizations an additional competitive advantage.

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